

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Genetic nature of some agronomic traits in two elite lines of rice

Bui Chi Buu and Phung Ba Tao, Cuulong Delta Rice Research Institute, Omon, Cantho, Vietnam

We studied the genetic nature of some agronomic traits using elite lines A 69-1 (P1) and IR31868-64-2-3-3-3 (P2) to efficiently exploit the variation in breeding materials. P1 combines well for salt tolerance. P2 is a high-yielding variety with good grain quality and resistance to major pests and diseases.

Thirty plants from the F₂ between the lines were randomly chosen. Each was backcrossed to its parents and to the F₁. The families of the P1, P2, F₁, F₂, BC₁ (F₁/P1), and BC₂ (F₁/P2) were studied. We transplanted and raised 10 plants from seeds of nonsegregating materials and 30 from seeds of segregating ones. The field experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design and replicated three times. Plants were spaced at 20 × 20 cm and fertilized at 80-40-0 kg NPK/ha.

Means of the studied traits were lower for F₂ than for F₁ and the better parent (Table 1). Backcrosses to the better parent produced higher values for all traits than backcrosses to the poorer parent. Results indicate scope for selecting parents and the possibility of getting heterotic lines.

Estimates of gene effects indicate highly significant dominance effects (Table 1). Additive × additive was significant among the epistasis effects.

Because dominance × dominance is large and negative and dominance large and positive, the estimates of additive, additive × additive, and additive × dominance should be mentioned without duplicate type of nonallelic interaction.

High variation occurs because of dominance and epistatic effects for all these traits. Selection in later generations

Table 1. Means of the basic generations and estimates of the genetic components.^a

Generation	Yield (g/plant)	Panicles (no./hill)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Panicle length (cm)	Plant height (cm)	Growth duration (d)
P1	19.6	9	95	30.2	27.4	114.0	135
P2	20.2	14	78	21.7	23.8	94.2	124
F ₁	33.5	14	119	27.3	26.2	114.9	133
F ₂	21.3	13	87	25.9	25.8	100.8	130
BC ₁	28.1	14	107	27.3	26.4	112.4	133
BC ₂	26.3	16	92	24.9	25.5	100.3	128
Estimate							
Mean	21.3**	13.1**	87.4**	25.9**	25.8**	100.8**	129.5**
Additive	1.8	-2.5	14.6	2.4*	0.9	12.1	4.5
Dominance	37.2**	10.1**	81.5**	2.2*	1.4**	33.0**	8.2*
Additive × additive	23.6**	7.6**	48.4**	0.8	0.5	22.2**	4.2*
Additive × dominance	2.0	0.0	5.9	-1.9	4.9	2.2	-1.0
Dominance × dominance	-25.6**	-16.5**	-35.3**	1.3	-0.7	-9.6*	-2.4

^a* and ** = significant at 5 and 1% levels.

Table 2. Equality test between the means of triple testcross families and basic generations.^a

Test	Yield	Panicles/hill	Filled grains/panicle	1000-grain wt	Panicle length	Plant ht	Growth duration
$\bar{L}_1 - \overline{BC}_1$	2.47*	0.85ns	-0.80ns	-0.20ns	0.38ns	-2.30ns	-0.90ns
$\bar{L}_2 - \overline{BC}_2$	-0.66ns	-1.10ns	-0.90ns	0.00ns	0.10ns	0.40ns	-0.20ns
$\bar{L}_3 - \bar{F}_3$	4.35**	2.04**	3.90ns	-1.00**	-0.20ns	-0.10ns	-1.40ns

^a* and ** = significance at 5 and 1% levels, ns = nonsignificant.

would be better to diminish dominance effects.

We tested for linkage by comparing the grand means of triple testcross families \bar{L}_1 (F₂/P1), \bar{L}_2 (F₂/P2), and \bar{L}_3 (F₂/F₁) and those of the basic generations

\overline{BC}_1 , \overline{BC}_2 , and \bar{F}_2 . Linked epistatic genes were present for all characters except grain yield (Table 2). The significant differences in grain yield expressed a linked digenic interaction. ■

Stability analysis for irrigated rice yield

S. S. Ali, S. J. H. Jafri, F. A. Faiz, S. Mehmood, and M. A. Butt, Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan

We evaluated the stability of the performance of 14 medium-grain advanced lines and varieties from 1989 to 1991. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted on 10 Jul 1989, 12 Jul 1990, and 10 Jul 1991. Plots were 2 × 6.25 m², with 30 cm between plants and rows. Recommended agronomic and plant protection measures

Mean grain yield (t/ha) and estimates of stability parameters for 14 rice genotypes over 3 yr.^a

Genotype	\bar{X}	bi	Sd ²	r ²
PK3699-43	3.33	1.1452	0.0718	0.0577
PK3717-9	4.33	0.9737	0.0659	0.0721
PK3717-12	4.19	1.9294	0.7997	0.0235
PK3727-2	3.92	1.4145**	0.0409**	0.0224
PK3727-5	3.73	2.0643**	0.1195**	0.0304
PK3732-8	3.41	0.9639	0.0242	0.0285
PK3733-7	3.19	0.7764	0.0287	0.0508
PK3737-10	3.39	0.6054	0.0223	0.0641
PK3737-11	3.51	1.1380	0.0406	0.0339
PK3801-18	3.53	1.1779	0.0450	0.0351
PK3917-33	3.60	1.1082	0.0686	0.0588
PK3849-18	3.66	0.9441	0.0648	0.0752
IR6	3.19	-0.0787	0.0537	0.9059
KS282	4.13	-0.1677	0.5099	0.9529
Av	3.65	1.0000		0.1722

^a** = significantly different from 0 at 0.01 level of probability.

were followed. We recorded yield at 14% moisture level.

The regression of genotypes for average yield on the environmental index resulted in regression coefficients (b) ranging from -0.1677 to 2.0643 (see table). The coefficient of determination (r^2) ranged from 0.0224 to 0.9529. The deviation from regression mean squares

($S^2 d$), a true measure of genotypic stability, ranged from 0.0223 to 0.7997.

PK3717-9, PK3727-2, PK3717-12, PK3727-5, PK3849-18, and KS282 showed higher yields than the pooled means, but they had varied responses to environmental fluctuations. PK3727-2 and PK3727-5 were unstable for yield because of the significant values of b_i and $S^2 d$.

PK3717-9, PK3717-12, and PK3849-18 yielded higher than the pooled mean. These genotypes also showed non-significant values for b_i and $S^2 d$, indicating stable genotype interaction over three environments. They can be recommended for use in breeding programs aiming to develop cultivars with high yield potential and better adaptability. □

Genetic studies for allogamous traits in *oryza sativa* L.

S. S. Ali, S. J. H. Jafri, M. G. Khan, and M. A. Butt. Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore. Pakistan

We studied the nature of the gene action of two traits—anther length and pollen grain size—in F_1 from a diallel cross involving the rice varieties and lines Basmati 370, Basmati 385, Basmati 198, and 4048.

We laid out the experiment during 1991 kharif in a randomized complete block design, with three replications, and a spacing of 30 cm between rows and plants. We measured anther length and pollen grain size using a binocular microscope and recorded 10 observations for both traits from each of the main panicles of 10 plants per replication for each genotype.

The components of variation (see table) revealed that additive component (D) exceeded the dominance components H_1 and H_2 for anther length, indicating additive type of gene action for increased anther length. The inverse, however, was true for pollen grain size. Recessive

Estimates of components of variation with their standard errors for anther length and pollen grain size in rice.

Anther length (mm)	Pollen grain size (μ)
$D \pm SE (D) = 0.0236 \pm 3.1623$	1.2795 ± 1.2669
$F \pm SE (F) = -0.0197 \pm 8.124$	1.3540 ± 3.2546
$H_1 \pm SE (H_1) = 0.0155 \pm 9.1924$	10.2192 ± 3.6826
$H_2 \pm SE (H_2) = 0.0090 \pm 8.4853$	8.0473 ± 3.3993
$h^2 \pm SE (h) = 4.0015 \pm 5.8310$	4.5319 ± 2.3305
$E \pm SE (E) = 0.002 \pm 0.4142$	0.727 ± 0.5666
Derived values	
$\sqrt{H_1/D}$	$= 0.8102 \quad 2.8261$
$H_2/4H_1$	$= 0.1457 \quad 0.1969$
$[\{4DH\}^{1/2} + F]/[\{4DH\}^{1/2} - F]$	$= 0.32 \quad 1.512$
h^2/H	$= -0.163 \quad 0.563$

alleles were important for anther length whereas more dominant alleles were observed for pollen grain size in parent varieties. H_1 and H_2 were not similar in both traits, showing that positive and negative allele frequencies were unequal.

The mean degree of dominance, 0.81 and 2.83, indicated partial dominance for anther length and overdominance for pollen grain size. The ratio of H_2 to $4H_1$

(0.14, 0.20) showed unequal positive and negative allele frequencies for both traits. The ratio h^2 to H_2 indicated that no dominant gene was controlling anther length whereas at least one gene controlling pollen grain size exhibited some dominance. This information will be useful in designing future hybrid rice breeding programs. □

Inheritance of aroma in two aromatic rice varieties

Huang He Qing and Zou Xue Ying, Hunan Rice Research Institute (HRRRI), Changsha, China

Jin-Long Dao and 80-66 are two later maturing aromatic rice varieties developed by HRRRI. We made reciprocal

crosses between these scented varieties and nonscented rice varieties HA8857 and Xiang Zao Xian no. 1 and 3 in 1989 to study aroma inheritance.

We sowed the F_1 and F_2 progeny and the parents from these crosses in Apr 1990 and transplanted them in May 1990. Thirty plants of each parent, 30 F_1 plants from each reciprocal cross, and about 200 F_2 plants of each cross from the four

Scent ratings of F_1 , F_2 , and parents, HRRRI, Changsha, China, 1990.

Entry	Plants (no.)			χ^2 (3:1)	P
	Total	Nonscented	Scented		
Parent					
Jin-Long Dao	30	0	30		
80-66	30	0	30		
Xiang zao Xian no. 1	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 3	30	30	0		
HA8557	30	30	0		
F_1					
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	30	30	0		
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 3	30	30	0		
Jin-Long Dao/HA8557	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 1/Jin-Long Dao	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 3/Jin-Long Dao	30	30	0		
HA8557/Jin-Long Dao	30	30	0		
80-66/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	30	30	0		
80-66/Xiang zao Xian no. 3	30	30	0		
80-66/HA8557	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 1/80-66	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 3/80-66	30	30	0		
HA8557/80-66	30	30	0		
F_2					
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	186	143	43	0.2580	0.50-0.75
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 3	160	124	36	0.4083	0.50-0.75
80-66/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	142	105	37	0.0375	>0.90
80-66/HA8557	161	124	37	0.4083	0.50-0.75